

Law Enforcement Related To Cyber-Pornography In Indonesian Criminal Justice System

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Abstract

This study aims to determine and analyze law enforcement efforts against internet pornography in Indonesia. The research involved the Yogyakarta Special Police, especially the Special Criminal Investigation Directorate; the State Attorney of Sleman, especially the General Crime Section; and the Sleman District Court, especially the Criminal Registry. The data for this study were collected through literature study, interviews and documentation. The data were analyzed by qualitative and quantitative analysis. The results showed that Law Number 44 Year 2008 regarding Pornography has been implemented fairly well. The implementation of the law starts from the stage of reporting and is followed by police investigation. However, the stage of reporting/complaint is likely to remain passive. Also, the stage of prosecuting criminal acts of pornography has been well implemented, by applying alternative charges to reduce the potential for mistakes in the application of the law during the hearing. In addition, the stage of trial of pornography related crimes has been done well, but there are still some constraints in getting experts.

Keywords: Law Enforcement; Pornography; Internet.

Introduction

The current era of globalization has had a huge impact on the advancement of information technology in all the countries of the world. Most developed countries take advantage of the advancement in information technology to sustain their national interests, while in developing and underdeveloped countries, the advancement of information technology seems to be an opportunity for a few people to profit in ways that are not justified by law, such as cheating by using fictitious accounts on social media, selling women by advertising prostitution on the internet, and selling or uploading pornographic content on the internet.

Indonesia is one of the economically and technologically advanced developing countries. In Indonesia, advances in information technology have also had a significant impact on the development of national law. The enactment of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 19 Year 2016 on the Amendment of Law of

the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 Year 2008 on Information and Electronic Transactions (ITE Law) is a proof of the development of Indonesia's national laws in the field of information technology, where the substance follows the development of the times and needs of the people of Indonesia. The ITE Law is the first law in the field of information technology and electronic transactions. It is a much-needed legislative product and has become a pioneer that lays the foundation of regulation in the field of utilization of information technology and electronic transactions.

The Internet makes conventional crimes, such as threats, theft, defamation, pornography, gambling, fraud and criminal acts of terrorism, easier. At present, through the internet, some types of criminal acts can be done by individuals or groups with very little risk of being caught. This leads to great losses for both communities and countries. The more interest people show in using the computer, the greater their dependence on the sophisticated equipment (Golose, 2006: 50). Globalization and the development of information technology affect many different crimes, and new crimes are now possible due to emerging technological developments. Crimes related to information technology are relatively new compared with other conventional crimes. Crimes related to information technology emerged along with the birth of the information technology revolution. Ronni R. Nitibaskara (2001: 38) stated the following:

"Social interaction that minimizes physical presence is another feature of the information technology revolution. With this kind of interaction, the deviation of crime social relationship will adjust its shape to that character. "

Cybercrime is one of the new forms or dimensions of today's crimes and has attracted widespread attention in the international world. Cybercrime is one of the dark sides of technological advances, and it has a very severe negative impact on all areas of modern life. Pornography is one of the forms of cybercrime. An important point that needs to be considered is that cybercrime is borderless, and so efforts to overcome and enforce the law must be maximal.

There are at least three main legislations governing the substance of the crime of internet pornography in Indonesia, and they are as follows:

1. Criminal Code;
2. Law no. 19 of 2016 on the Amendment to Law No. 11 of 2008 on Information and Electronic Transactions; and
3. Law no. 44 of 2008 on Pornography (Pornography Act).

Of the three laws and regulations that form the main basis of the substance of pornography crime, only the Pornography Act provides a clear definition of what Pornography is. Article 1 number 1 states as follows:

"Pornography is a drawing, sketch, illustration, photo, writing, sound, motion picture, animation, cartoon, conversation, gesture or other forms of message through various forms of communication media and/or public performances containing obscenity or sexual exploitation that violates moral norms in society".

The crime of internet pornography is punishable by Article 281 up to Article 297 of the Criminal Code, Article 27 paragraph (1) of the ITE Law, and Article 29 paragraph (1) of the Pornography Act. Many pornographic materials are circulated through the internet, and because the internet is without boundaries, such materials can be accessed in all regions of Indonesia and even all over the world.

With respect to pornography crimes, some cases have been decided by the courts. Reza Rizaldy aka Rejoy bin Imam Santosa was sentenced to two years and six months imprisonment after been proven guilty beyond reasonable doubt of committing a criminal act of allowing others to spread pornography. Another case was decided by the Bandung District Court, who sentenced the defendant, Nazril Irham aka Ariel Peterpan, to three years and six months imprisonment. Further, the Sleman District Court convicted Herman Joseph bin Ie Hie Soeng after it was proven beyond reasonable doubt that the defendant was guilty of the crime of transmitting electronic information whose content violates decency. Similarly, cases of transmitting sexual content of minors have been exposed by the police. Metro Jaya Regional Police revealed a case of spreading child pornography content conducted using social media, a Facebook account named Official Candys Group.

Stage of Investigation

Pornography has become one of the most complicated issues in law enforcement. This is because of its massive spread, and it is very difficult to handle. With the introduction of the internet, it has become a challenge for law enforcers to eradicate pornography. The crime of cyberporn (pornography on the internet) has a massive impact. Cyberporn can be categorized as a cybercrime. But in classifying cyberporn as a cybercrime, reference is made to only the perpetrators of spreading pornography or those who provide pornographic links on the internet, and there is also the aspect of downloading and spreading it. In the chain, after the first spreader or the first link provider, it is worthy and interesting to examine whether the others are perpetrators or victims. This problem can be analyzed using crime without victim reviews to see if they are true victims or just actors. This article will discuss whether cyberporn can be seen in the review as well as review who is actually a victim in the massive deployment of cyberporn at this time, so that a cyberporn prevention policy can be formulated (Putra, 2018).

Due to the enactment of the ITE Law on April 21, 2008, Indonesia now has a special law that regulates all acts committed using the internet. There are arrangements in the field of criminal law, both in terms of material criminal law, contained in Chapter VII, article 27-37 of the ITE Law, and the aspect of formal

criminal law, contained in Chapter X, Article 42 - 44 of the ITE Law. The formal regulation of criminal law, specifically the ITE Law, shows that there is an understanding of the difference in handling of criminal cases of information and electronic transactions, including criminal acts of internet pornography. It is just that the regulation in the ITE Law related to formal criminal law does not elaborate in detail what procedure should be applied by law enforcers in criminal cases of information and electronic transactions. Law enforcement in the event of a criminal case should be done in a series of legal proceedings, from investigation to prosecution, court hearing, decisions, and legal remedies.

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